

POLYMER COMPOSITES REINFORCED BY CONTINUOUS IRREGULAR NETWORKS: FROM BIOINSPIRED DESIGN TO FRACTURE

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ABSTRACT

Biological materials are often reinforced by irregular structures that provide outstanding mechanical properties, ranging from high stiffness-to-weight ratios to excellent energy absorption. Unfortunately, replicating the complex design of non-periodic biological structures in synthetic materials still proves a significant design and fabrication challenge. In this context, the recent development of virtual growth algorithms, a tile-based material design tool, can pave the way to a new class of bioinspired architected materials, with superior structural properties. The algorithms can independently tailor the global topology and the local geometry of the generated structures, allowing precise control over the final mechanical properties of the generated materials. Using the algorithm, polymer composites can be designed and then fabricated by additive manufacturing, achieving control over global mechanical properties, like strength and rigidity, as well as local mechanisms of fracture nucleation and propagation, and of fracture energy dissipation. Furthermore, VGAs can be used for bioinspired materials design, by converting complex non-periodic biological structures into a network of building blocks and rules that determine their relative connectivity. Rather than creating an exact replica of the biological material, the method generates synthetic polymer composites with equivalent global- and local descriptors to the biological material, allowing for the emergence of analogous structure-to-property relationships. The method is demonstrated using the pericarp of an orange, a biological material known for its high energy-absorbing capabilities and its gradual rigidity variations. Starting from high resolution micrographs of the biological material, design guidelines for the creation of materials inspired by the orange pericarp can be extracted. Using additive manufacturing, orange-inspired polymer composites can be fabricated and tested under quasi-static and dynamic compressive loading. While the quasi-static results reveal spatially varying mechanical properties, dynamic loading experiments highlight the local mechanisms of deformation responsible for the dissipation of impact energy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the process of evolution, nature has generated a multitude of materials that display excellent mechanical properties, ranging from high rigidity, load-bearing capacity, resistance against the initiation and propagation of fractures, and resistance against unpredictable impacts. Using readily available resources, nature achieves these properties by fine-tuning the internal architecture of the materials, arranging reinforcing elements, such as particles, rods, and platelets, in complex and often hierarchical assemblies. Bone and mother-of-pearl are examples of such hierarchically reinforced materials, whose mechanical properties exceed those of their constituents. Nacre, another name for mother-of-pearl, is the inner lining of pen, oysters and abalone shells, and is composed of 95% of calcium carbonate platelets, in the form of aragonite. Despite aragonite is a brittle constituent, nacre displays a fracture resistance that is two orders of magnitude higher than its monolithic equivalent. This remarkable improvement in fracture resistance is due to the internal arrangement of the platelets, organized in a highly regular and periodic, brick-and-mortar configuration [1]. This structure can deflect incoming cracks on long and tortuous trajectories, dissipating enormous amounts of fracture energy. Over the last decades, efforts have targeted the reproduction, at the laboratory scale, of brick-and-mortar architectures, leveraging

freeze casting,[2], [3] magnetic alignment,[4], [5], [6] and gravitational sedimentation,[7], [8], [9] as means to control the alignment of large aspect ratio reinforcing elements in high-volume fraction nacre-inspired composites. Replicating the internal architecture of biological nacre in synthetic composites, using high-performance ceramics, like alumina or glass, has enabled the design and manufacturing of composites which display a combination of strength, stiffness, and toughness, properties that are often mutually exclusive in manmade materials.[10] Similarly to nacre, the club of the mantis shrimp and cortical bone[11], [12], [13] are other examples of materials that display periodic internal architectures, with their reinforcing elements arranged in Bouligand or in concentric lamellar domains, respectively.

Periodic bioinspired materials have been widely studied and replicated in the laboratories, due to their ease of manufacturing, through particle-assembly methods or additive manufacturing. However, nature does not always resort to highly periodic structures for its structural materials. Trabecular bone[14], [15] and the citrus fruit pericarp[16] are examples of biological structural materials that display a highly irregular, non-periodic internal architecture. Trabecular bone, also called spongy bone, constitutes the highly porous internal portion of our bones. It is formed by trabecular struts and plates, and despite its mechanical properties are highly dependent on its mineral and collagen content, it is critical to transfer stresses to cortical (or compact) bone and to carry loads, while maintaining an overall low weight.[17] Fruit pericarps are instead formidable impact absorbers. When the fruits fall from the tree, citrus fruit pericarps protect the pulp and the seeds, efficiently absorbing impact energy and leaving the fruit intact. Taking inspiration from irregular biological structural materials and replicating their complex structures using higher-performance engineering constituents is extremely relevant, from safety critical applications, where preventing damage from impacts with objects is paramount, to soft robotics and smart skins, where damage avoidance is critical for object manipulation and human-robot interactions.

Unfortunately, replicating the internal structure of an irregular biological material is complex. High-fidelity replication requires microcomputed tomography[18], [19] or investment casting.[20] Stochastic processes, like foaming,[21], [22] prove limited, because they are often unable to imitate the complex internal structure of the biological material, as well as its structural logic. In this context, computational approaches, like tile-based assembly methods and virtual growth algorithms, VGAs, can provide the level of control that is necessary to replicate the irregular arrangement of domains across lengthscales and their spatially varying density, critical aspects when replicating the internal architecture of biological materials.

In this work, I will highlight a VGA-based material design method that recently emerged as a promising platform to replicate non-periodic biological materials and to generate non-periodic reinforcing materials architectures. Starting from the pericarp of an orange, its irregular structure is discretized into a network of tiles, connected through a precise set of connectivity rules, allowing the generation of countless equivalent irregular architectures that display analogous topology, the connectivity between adjacent tiles, and geometry, the shape of the generated domains or mesostructures. The generated materials are then fabricated using additive manufacturing and tested in quasi-static and dynamic compression, with the goal of determining their architecture-to-properties relationship, along with the role of the tiles or of their assembly into mesostructures, on the global and local mechanical response of the materials.

2 METHODS AND RESULTS

2.1 Tile-based Material Generation: Virtual Growth Algorithms

Virtual Growth Algorithms (VGAs) are a powerful platform for materials design and generation that gained significant traction for their ability to develop non-periodic structures and networks through local growth processes, that have been recently exploited for the generation of reinforcing networks in composites and lattices. Introduced by Liu and co-authors, VGAs are graph-based and rely on the assembly of simplified building blocks, or tiles.[23] The assembly of the tiles occurs stochastically over a predefined grid or mesh, following a precise set of connectivity or adjacency rules, paramount to determine the tile-to-tile connections that are allowed or not. The final structure that is generated depends on the geometry and connectivity of the tiles, as well as on their availability and relative connectivity

(Figure 1). These are all inputs that are provided by the user. As a result, VGAs are extremely powerful as they allow to decouple the topology of the network, or its connectivity, and its geometry, emerging from the shape of the chosen tiles. The VGAs developed by Liu and co-authors implemented a *WaveFunctionCollapse* algorithm.[24] The structure gets formed iteratively; the algorithm evaluates eligible sites for growth and selects the location with the minimal nodal entropy for the next tile assignment. For each location, the nodal entropy depends on the total number of tiles that satisfies the connectivity rules. As the structure gets formed, structural features, also called mesostructures, emerge. Preventing the formation of mesostructures that are disconnected from the rest of the network is paramount, and connections that can lead to closed-loops are often forbidden.

Figure 1: Sketch depicting the virtual growth algorithm and its working principle. Figure adapted from Magrini et al.[25] and Fox et al.[26]

2.2 Bioinspired Materials Generation

2-dimensional cross-sectional microscopy images of the pericarp of an orange were retrieved. The detailed procedure to cut and stain the biological tissues for histological imaging has been carefully reported by Fox and co-authors.[26] Orange pericarps display a density gradient, as they are composed by two primary regions. The external region, called flavedo, is rigid and highly interconnected. The internal region, called albedo, contains large intercellular spaces, that due to their high compressibility are responsible for the great energy absorbing capability of the pericarp (Figure 2).[27], [28]

Figure 2: The orange pericarp (cross-sectional view). Microscopy image credits: M. Antonini.

Leveraging the image processing software Fiji,[29] the histological cross-section of the pericarp is first converted into a skeleton,[30] a line with a single pixel thickness. The skeleton is then subdivided into a collection of irregular tiles, using a regular grid. The size of the grid elements is chosen to ensure that no more than one node per element is included (Figure 3a). Despite each tile extracted from the biological material is irregular and different from the neighbouring ones, a conversion must be carried out, with the goal of simplifying the extracted tile into one of the five pre-selected VGA-tiles. This

conversion is performed by analyzing the perimeter of the irregular tiles, and assigning a value to each intersection of the branches with the external perimeter. Using binary code values, 1, 10, 100 and 1000, representing left, top, right and bottom respectively, it is possible to uniquely assign a simplified VGA-tile equivalent to each irregular element extracted from the starting image. Each simplified VGA-tile is defined by its coordination number, the number of connections it forms, and its orientation (Figure 3b).

Figure 3: The conversion method. a) Image processing to extract the irregular tiles from the skeletonized image. b) Conversion in simplified VGA-tiles and relative connectivity rules (examples).
Figure adapted from Fox et al.[26]

Once all grid elements have been converted into simplified VGA-tiles, the connections between VGA-tiles are analysed, with the goal of determining the connectivity rules that allow the reconstruction of the orange peel. As expected, the composition, intended as the frequency of each simplified VGA-tile, as well as the rules that determine the connectivity between the tiles, both depend on the region of the pericarp that is studied. For example, the flavedo region of the pericarp features a higher frequency of 3- and 4-coordinated tiles than the albedo region. This is representative of the higher density and interconnectivity of the external layer of the pericarp. On the other hand, the albedo region features a higher frequency of empty tiles, due to the presence of larger intercellular spaces in the inner portion of the peel (Figure 4a). Analogous conclusions can be drawn from the extracted connectivity rules. The flavedo-inspired portion features a higher frequency of 3-to-3 coordinated tiles and 3-to-2 coordinated tiles connections than the albedo-inspired portion, while the empty-to-empty tile connections are more representative in the albedo than in the flavedo (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Extracting tile composition and connectivity rules from the orange pericarp. a) Tile frequency. b) Examples of the connectivity rules. Figure adapted from Fox et al.[26]

2.3 Material Fabrication

With the tile frequencies and connectivity rules extracted from the flavedo and albedo portions of the pericarp, the virtual growth algorithm is used to reconstruct flavedo-inspired (F) VGA-samples and albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples, with a size of 50-by-50 tiles. As the flavedo accounts for 10-20% of the overall peel thickness, and the albedo for the remaining 80-90%, the generated structures are then combined, recreating the full-pericarp (P) VGA-samples (Figure 5). To carry out the mechanical characterization of the structures, samples with a height of 2.5 cm, width of 2.5 cm and thickness of 1.0 cm were manufactured using a polyjet printer (Stratasys Objet500 Connex3), using two commercially available photoreins, Stratasys VeroWhite Polyjet Resin (VW) and Stratasys TangoBlack Polyjet Resin (TB). VW, a stiff viscoelastic polymer, is used for the reinforcing network, while TB, a soft elastomeric polymer, is used for the matrix, filling the gaps within the network. Accounting for the limitation of the polyjet printer, a tile size of 0.5 mm by 0.5 mm was chosen, with individual network struts of 0.1 mm. In this study, contrary to the biological material, generating a two-phase material was preferred, leading to polymer-composite specimens suitable for mechanical testing and for mapping of strains through 2D digital image correlation (DIC). The mechanical properties of the resins used in this study fall within the ranges reported in literature. [31], [32]

Figure 5: VGA-generated samples: (F), (A), and (P). Flavedo-, Albedo-, and full-Pericarp inspired samples. Figure adapted from Fox et al.[26]

2.4 Quasi-static Mechanical Testing: Compression

Quasi-static mechanical testing was carried out using a universal testing machine (UTS) (Instron E3000, Instron, USA), with a 5kN load cell equipped with flat compression plates, at a rate of 1mm/min and up to a 10% compressive strain. Three set of samples have been tested: flavedo-inspired (F) VGA-samples, albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples, and full-pericarp (P) VGA-samples. From the stress-strain curves, the modulus of elasticity was extracted. As one could expect from their biological counterparts, the F-samples proved 116% stiffer than the A-samples, while P-samples displayed intermediate values (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves recorded on flavedo-inspired (F) VGA-samples (left), albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples (middle) and full-pericarp (P) VGA-samples (right). Adapted from Fox et al.[26]

To determine the role of local mesostructures (the local domains formed by adjacent VGA-tiles) during compression loading, 2D DIC was performed to track the strain field. The composites were spray painted using a flat white paint and speckled with flat black paint, generating a speckle size of 0.1 to 0.3 mm. Commercially available DIC software (VIC 2D, Correlated Solutions, USA) was used to reconstruct the Lagrangian strain field (subset size 35, step size 2). Through DIC it was possible to elucidate the strain distribution during compressive loading. Up to 10% global compressive strain, F-samples displayed uniform strain fields, without exceeding 15% strain at the local scale (Figure 7a). This is due to the extensive presence of stretching-dominated mesostructures, formed by high-coordination tiles (3- and 4-coordinated tiles). On the contrary, A-samples displayed highly localized strain field, with mesostructures reaching up to 30% local strain, at an applied 10% global compressive strain (Figure 7b). This was observed in large and highly compressible mesostructures, composed of consecutive low-coordination tiles (2-coordinated tiles and empty tiles). These mesostructures often featured concave edges and 2-coordinated tiles arranged diagonally in series, which can rotate, during deformation, around 3-coordinated nodes.

Figure 7: Compression tests. 2D DIC recorded at 0%, 5% and 10% global strain on flavedo-inspired (F) VGA-samples (a) and albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples (b). Figure adapted from Fox et al.[26]

2.5 Dynamic Mechanical Testing: Compression

Finally, the energy absorption capabilities of the samples were characterized using drop tower tests conducted at a strain rate of $\sim 100 \text{ s}^{-1}$. For the purpose, a drop tower of 3 m height and 2.7 cm inner diameter and a cylindrical striker of 10 cm height, 2.5 cm diameter and a 400 g mass were chosen. The experiments were recorded using a high-speed camera (Phantom v1610, Vision Research, AMETEK, USA), triggered by a photodiode mounted in proximity of the tower's lower opening, set to an acquisition rate of 50k fps at a resolution of 512 pixel by 512 pixel (Figure 8a). Analysing the recorded videos with the image processing software Fiji,[29] the time in contact between the striker and the sample, along with the coefficient of restitution (e), defined as the ratio between the velocity of the striker before and after the impact with the sample, were extracted (Figure 8b and 8c). The results were compared to periodic honeycomb (H) and graded honeycomb (gH) samples having the same volume fraction of reinforcing phase. Among all the conducted tests, the flavedo-inspired (F) VGA-samples displayed the highest e and the shortest time in contact with the striker. On the other hand, the full-pericarp (P) VGA-samples, similarly to the albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples, displayed a 7.5% and 10% lower e than the H- and gH-samples respectively. In parallel to a lower coefficient of restitution,

(P)- and (A) VGA-samples display a 16% and 25% longer time in contact with the striker with respect to H- and gH-samples, respectively. Such a striking difference in energy absorption performance is due to the reinforcing architecture of the materials. There is indeed a correlation between the mesostructures size and shape, and the deformation they are subjected to during compressive loading. For example, the presence of large, concave mesostructures formed by low coordination tile assemblies, often observed in the albedo-inspired (A) VGA-samples (and therefore in the full-pericarp (P) VGA-samples), leads to less constrained strut bending and buckling. These mechanisms of deformation, already observed in the quasi-static compression loading tests, are analogous to what is observed in the biological material counterpart, where large and compressible intercellular spaces in the orange albedo are responsible of dissipating most of the energy caused by unpredictable impacts, like when the fruit falls from the tree.

Figure 8: a) time-lapse of the striker impact on a full-pericarp (P) VGA-sample. b) The measured coefficient of restitution. c) The recorded time in contact. Figure adapted from Fox et al.[26]

3 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, using computer-aided tile-based material design methods, it is possible to extract the topology and the geometry of irregular biological materials, like the pericarp of an orange, and recreate their structure-to-properties relationship in bioinspired equivalents. The bioinspired structures are fabricated using multi-material additive manufacturing and tested in quasi-static and dynamic compression. Using DIC and image analysis, it is possible to analyze the mechanisms of deformation that occur at the local scale, correlate them to the global mechanical performance of the materials and to the mesostructures that emerge during sample generation.

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